

[original idea]

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Superposition as a mathematical mapping between two distinct scales

Open Physics Collaboration*†

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Abstract

A toy model is presented connecting the Planck with the macroscopic scale through a mathematical mapping to explain quantum superposition at a more fundamental level.

keywords: quantum superposition, mathematical mapping, Planck scale, quantum gravity, spacetime

The most updated version of this white paper is available at
<https://osf.io/uksgx/download>
<https://zenodo.org/record/7626569>

Introduction

1. Quantum superposition appears in nature at a variety of forms [1].
2. In space, an electron can occupy multiple locations at once.
3. In spacetime, an electron can travel at multiple trajectories at once.
4. (3) is the quantum superposition of trajectories, known as the path integral formulation of quantum mechanics [2].

*All *authors* with their *affiliations* appear at the end of this white paper.

†Corresponding author: mp1obo@uft.edu.br | **Open Physics Collaboration**

5. In the following sections, we present a toy model as a mathematical mapping connecting two different scales.

Open Question

6. How is it possible that an electron moves both clockwise and counter-clockwise at the same time?
7. We try to address this question in a pure mathematical approach [3].

Mathematical mapping

8. Let $f : Q \rightarrow C$, where Q is the set of *quantum pieces of spacetime* at the Planck scale and C is the *classical units of spacetime* at the macroscopic level (usually denoted as the real numbers).
9. The mapping f connects “positions” in the quantum realm with classical positions.

The toy model

10. Consider the quantum object confined in one dimension of space (x).
11. Suppose that $f(x) = |x|$.
12. f means that for $x = \pm a$, the same output is produced (a).
13. The interpretation of this very simplistic toy model is that the same “position” at the classical level can be represented by two different and symmetric positions of space in the quantum level.

Final Remarks

14. We presented a very simple way of understanding how quantum superposition can operate at the classical world by means of a simple mathematical model.
15. Evidently, nature operates in a more complex way (with an overwhelming mixture of robust functions and other mathematical structures as well).
16. We hope that this work originates fruitful outcomes in the near future.
17. Some discussions on quantum superposition can be found here [4–6].

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [7,8].

Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.

Send your contribution to `mplobo@uft.edu.br`.

Supplementary files

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [9,10].

How to cite this paper?

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Agreement

The author agrees with [8].

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The Open Physics Collaboration

Matheus Pereira Lobo¹ (lead author, mplobo@uft.edu.br)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4554-1372>

¹Federal University of Northern Tocantins (Brazil)